

COMPLETE RESPONSE TO LONSURF IN A STAGE IV RIGHT SIDED COLON CANCER PATIENT WITH PERITONEAL METASTASIS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Right-sided colon cancer continues to be the third most frequently occurring cancer and a primary cause of cancer-related deaths globally. The 5-year relative survival rate for patients diagnosed with stage IV Right-sided colon cancer is only 14 percent. **Case**

Report: A 53-year-old non-diabetic non-alcoholic, nonsmoker, male patient was diagnosed with stage IV right-sided colon cancer with ascites, and peritoneal metastasis. The patient has no significant past medical history. The patient presented to the emergency department with major complaints of generalized abdominal pain associated with persistent nausea and vomiting. According to the esophageal-gastro-

duodenoscopy report, the gastric outlet was partially obstructed by compression from outside. The patient presented to emergency department at Mafraq Hospital Abu Dhabi on 25/4/2019. CT scan showed multiple peritoneal deposits with ascites. CT-guided peritoneal biopsy reported as metastatic mucinous adenocarcinoma. Tumor cells were negative for CK7, Calretinin, and WT1. However, the other biomarkers CK20, BerEP4, MOC31, and CDX2 were found to be positive. On 26/8/2019, he underwent exploratory laparotomy, cytoreductive surgery, and Hyperthermic intraperitoneal chemotherapy with Mitomycin C. After the surgery, tumor marker carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) was found to be persistently high 11.80 mcg/L. The patient was given 6 cycles of Folfox and Avastin as first-line palliative chemotherapy. He responded to this treatment plan initially but the tumor progressed, then he was switched to second-line therapy FOLFIRI and Ramucirumab. He also responded to this therapy initially but later his condition worsened. Then, he received

Lonsurf as third-line palliative therapy. Lonsurf was found to be very effective in this case. The amazing thing about this treatment approach was that his disease was completely cleared up and he had been in complete remission for almost 2 years. **Conclusion:** Our case report demonstrated a full response to Lonsurf in a patient with stage IV right-sided colon cancer, ascites, and peritoneal metastasis.

KEYWORDS: Trifluridine-tipiracil, Lonsurf, Stage IV colon cancer, Colorectal cancer, ascites, Peritoneal metastasis.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, colon cancer is the major cause of cancer-related deaths, and its incidence has been rising since 2015.^[1] Patients with Stage IV colon cancer/ colorectal cancer have a 12.5–17.8% 5-year survival rate.^[2] In particular, patients with Stage IV colon cancer who develop peritoneal spread which has a poor prognosis. According to the studies, the median cancer-specific survival of individuals with peritoneal metastases was lower than that of individuals with single-organ metastases at sites other than the peritoneum and was similar to individuals with multiple-organ metastases.^[3] Peritoneal spread is seen in 4–10% of all CRCs, with the majority being T3 or T4 CRCs.^[4] There are currently few therapy options available for patients with stage IV colon cancer who develop resistance to or intolerance to first- and second-line medications.

One of these options is Lonsurf therapy. Trifluridine-tipiracil (Lonsurf) is an orally administered combination of the anticancer nucleoside analog trifluridine (FTD) and the thymidine phosphorylase inhibitor tipiracil (TPI).^[5] It has been proposed that the incorporation of trifluridine (FTD) into DNA ultimately results in double-helical DNA breakage. Tipiracil (TPI) enhances the efficacy of FTD by preserving the blood concentration of FTD by blocking the thymidine phosphorylase responsible for FTD breakdown.^[6]

Tipiracil has both an anti-angiogenic and potentiating action on trifluridine. In the RECURSE study, Lonsurf demonstrated efficacy vs placebo in patients with refractory metastatic cancer, increasing overall survival from 5.3 months to 7.1 months with a hazard ratio (HR) of 0.68.^[7] The progression-free survival (PFS) was enhanced with a 0.48 hazard ratio. Additionally, according to this study, the response rate was only 1.6%, while the rate of illness control, which includes stable disease, was 44%, compared to 16% in the placebo group. This suggests that Tipiracil may be an effective treatment for advanced colon cancer.

However, a cure for colorectal cancer along with metastasis is still uncommon. Here, we report a case of stage IV colon cancer complicated by peritoneal ascites that showed complete response to third-line therapy with Lonsurf.

CASE REPORT

A 53-year-old non-diabetic non-alcoholic, nonsmoker, male patient was diagnosed with stage IV right-sided colon cancer, ascites, and peritoneal metastasis. Previously, the patient presented to the emergency department in Sudan with major complaints of generalized abdominal pain associated with persistent nausea and vomiting. The patient was assessed for these symptoms. At that time, the patient's diagnosis was H.Pylori infection and typhoid, for which he received treatment. However, no significant improvement was noted in the patient's condition. Later, the patient was suggested to undergo an Ultrasound abdomen. The findings revealed possible Duodenal obstruction. After that, the patient underwent Oesophago-Gastro-Duodenoscopy and was told he is having Partial Gastric outlet obstruction possibly due to a tumor compressing from outside. Although no biopsies were performed. At that time, the doctor advised him to undergo a CT scan of the abdomen. The findings of the CT scan revealed similar findings in the Ultrasound abdomen.

Later, on 25 April 2019, the patient was presented to the Emergency department of Mafraq Hospital Abu Dhabi with a major complaint of an abdominal pain. This case was discussed with the Gastrointestinal department team and the patient was suggested to undergo Oesophago-Gastro-Duodenoscopy. So, on 29 April 2019, the Oesophago-Gastro-Duodenoscopy was performed. The findings suggested a diagnosis of Hiatus Hernia and esophagitis. After that, on 1 May 2019, the patient underwent Intervention radiology Paracentesis. The procedure came negative for malignancy. Moreover, gastric endoscopy was performed. The findings revealed: Antral/body type mucosa, no intestinal metaplasia, no active chronic gastritis, and Warthin starry stain was found to be negative for H. pylori-like organisms. This indicated that the patient's symptoms were due to the tumor rather than an infection caused by H pylori.

After 6 days, on 7th May 2019, the patient underwent a peritoneal biopsy. The findings of the peritoneal biopsy pathology profile revealed: - Mucinous neoplasm of low-grade malignancy. At this time, the patient had developed low-grade malignancy as findings of the biopsy revealed common features suggestive of Carcinomatosis mucinous peritonei. Although the current small biopsy showed low-grade features, doctors suggested that final grading should

be obtained from a resection specimen. CK7 was found to be negative. However, in the cytology report, the other biomarkers CK20, BerEP4, MOC31, and CDX2 were found to be positive indicating high suspicion of carcinoma. On the other hand, Calretinin and WT1 were found to be negative. This cytology report came on 15 May 2019. Additionally, it was revealed that appearances were consistent with metastatic adenocarcinoma of colorectal origin.

Again, after two months, on 4 July 2019, the patient presented to the emergency department with the same complaint of Abdominal pain. This time patient also complained about a loss of appetite. He also told the doctor that he had lost weight of around 15 kg over the past 6 months with no major change in bowel habits.

In the next following month, on 26 August 2019, the patient underwent exploratory laparotomy, cytoreductive surgery (right hemicolectomy, omentectomy, peritonectomy, excision of umbilical nodule and falciform), and HIPEC with Mitomycin C.

After a few days of surgical procedure, on 19 September 2019, the patient underwent further testing to rule out remaining pathologies. Pathology profile revealed: Grade 2 moderately differentiated mucinous adenocarcinoma of the appendix, the background of high-grade mucinous neoplasm (HG MN) about 8 cm in maximum dimension, signs of Lymph vascular invasion, involvement of mesenteric and distal margins, involvement of Mesoappendix and omentum, tumor infiltration including the full thickness of the ileum, involvement of 10 out of 29 lymph nodes (pT4B N2 M1c).

Other findings were: RUQ peritoneum, involved by mucinous adenocarcinoma, RLQ peritoneum: involved by mucinous adenocarcinoma, Omentum: involved by mucinous adenocarcinoma, Falciform ligament: involved by mucinous adenocarcinoma, Umbilical nodule: metastatic mucinous adenocarcinoma and on right lower limb skin tag: no Fibroepithelial polyp, no dysplasia or malignancy was seen.

Additionally, on 23 September 2019, a Microsatellite instability MSI test was conducted which showed no loss of nuclear expression of MMR proteins (No evidence of deficient mismatch repair). Moreover, a low probability of microsatellite instability-high (MSI-H) was found. However, the patient was found to have mutations in the KRAS gene on 21 October

2019. Furthermore, tumor markers such as carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) was found to be very high at 11.80 mcg/L postoperatively.

Later, on 2nd February 2020, a CT Scan chest abdomen, and pelvis with Contrast was performed. The findings revealed upper anterior mediastinal lymph node involvement. However, no significant changes in the appearance of the nodule of the right lung were noted. Additionally, there were signs of persistent left upper quadrant peritoneal metastasis. At that time, it was not possible to comment on the chemotherapy response because previous CT chest scans were not available. The patient was given 6 cycles of Folfox + Avastin as First line palliative chemotherapy. The patient completed 6 cycles of FOLFOX Chemotherapy on 14 April 2020. Additionally, on 28 April 2020 5FU + Avastin Chemo, maintenance Immunotherapy (Day 1 and 15) was started, later it was switched to q 3 weekly initiated on cycle 3 due to the development of proteinuria.

Moreover, on 19 April 2020, after 6 cycles of Folfox + Avastin CT Scan Neck chest abdomen, and pelvis was performed. The findings revealed non-specific sub-centimeter level 1 lymph nodes appreciated bilaterally and interval increase in the size of the anterior mediastinal lymph. However, no interval of new lymph nodes was observed in the mediastinum, hilar or axillary region. Additionally, the results were difficult to characterize. On 19th August 2020, the patient completed 5 cycles of maintenance 5FU + Avastin chemo-immunotherapy.

Furthermore, on 7th July 2020, a CT Scan chest abdomen, and pelvis revealed no major pathological findings. Overall findings represented stable disease. CT Scan chest abdomen and pelvis was also repeated at the end of the year, on 16 December 2020, which did not indicate any significant interval change in terms of soft tissue lesions, bowel, lymph node, or visceral abnormality. CT report also showed redemonstration of findings of peritoneal carcinomatosis which was unchanged in extent. However, there was an interval appearance of moderate ascites in the abdomen and pelvis raising the suspicion of progression of the peritoneal disease.

Therefore, on 13 September 2020, FOLFIRI + Ramucirumab as a 2nd Line of treatment was administered via port-a-catheter on the 1st and 15th days.

Later, on 1st January 2021, the patient was again presented to the emergency department with a major complaint of hematemesis. The patient was admitted under the supervision of the medical team and further investigation was done. Immediately, OGD was performed which showed: Reflux esophagitis most likely the cause of his hematemesis, esophageal varices without any bleeding signs, and splenomegaly without cirrhosis. Additionally, there were signs of gastritis. After the diagnosis, at the end of this month, on 31 January 2021, the patient completed 5 Cycles (Day 1 and DAY 15) of FOLFIRI as a 2nd Line chemotherapy via a pump. Ramcirumab was put on hold due to upper GI bleeding

Then again, on 9 Feb 2021, the patient was admitted to the hospital due to complaints of weakness and fatigue. At that time, the patient was diagnosed with Covid-19 infection and was treated accordingly. Additionally, due to the progression of the disease radiologically and clinically we could not give any more VEGFR inhibitors (due to upper GI bleeding). Therefore, we decided to switch treatment to Lonsurf oral chemotherapy as 3rd line treatment. The patient started to receive Lonsurf oral chemotherapy on 25/2/2021. After receiving Lonsurf, the patient seemed vitally stable. Blood tests were found to be normal. Additionally, it was clearly shown that CEA levels were fluctuating from 56 >> 48, 85 and later dropped to around 50 mcg/l. Moreover, Urine protein levels improved to 0.67 g/l. However, liver enzymes were found to be elevated. The patient was advised to undergo a CT scan. CT scan revealed unremarkable changes. The patient seemed to be performing better as he was less complaining about abdominal discomfort, nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea. Additionally, there were no other signs of Dyspepsia and Hypocalcemia.

Later, on 26 June 2021, a CT scan was performed which revealed a distended stomach with epigastric thickening around the antrum and pylorus and resolution of the ascites. All these findings were suggestive of stable metastatic disease.

Again, on 9 October 2021, a CT scan chest abdomen, and pelvis was performed which indicated unremarkable changes suggestive of stable disease. It showed also resolution of the soft tissue thickening around the antrum and the pylorus of the stomach since the previous scan. No new lesion seen. The patient hemoglobin level improved to 12.5, and tumor marker CEA dropped down to 53 mcg/l.

A re-evaluation computerized tomography scan performed on 1 July 2022 indicated stable disease. As expected, the outcomes were favorable, resulting in a significant improvement in

the patient's symptoms and overall condition. All tumor markers decreased again and normalized and the patient was reassured. The latest clinical visit was on January 2023 where patient presented with signs and symptoms of partial intestinal obstruction. A computerized tomography scan showed progressive disease with signs of increase peritoneal metastasis ascites and signs of small intestinal obstruction. At that time patient was off Lonsurf due to personal reason. Lonsurf was re-initiated and Avastin was added.

DISCUSSION

Colorectal cancer is one of the most prevalent diseases worldwide and it is the fourth most prevalent cancer among both women and men in Asian countries.^[8] For example, in Korea and Japan, colorectal cancer is the third most frequently occurring cancer, the second most prevalent disease among males, and the third most prevalent cancer among women.^[9] Additionally, Peritoneal metastasis is one of the primary causes of death associated with colon cancer and is frequently difficult to treat. According to population-based data, the median survival time after a diagnosis of peritoneal metastasis is six months (1) However, in our case, the patient has survived for almost 4 years and is still alive.

Furthermore, the risk factors for developing peritoneal metastases from colon cancer are mucinous adenocarcinoma, right-sided colon cancer, lymph node metastases, age less than 70–75 years old, synchronous ovarian metastases (in female), emergency surgery at diagnosis, and incomplete primary tumor resection.^[10,11] In our case, five risk factors were found, mucinous adenocarcinoma, right-sided colon cancer, advanced T stage, and young age. Additionally, lymph node metastases were also noted in CRC along with peritoneal spread as pathology profile revealed positive involvement of 10 out of 29 lymph nodes (pT4B N2 M1c). Studies have also reported that lymph node metastases along with CRC, occur in 1.0 percent of cases^[12] and they may be a significant risk factor.

The current mainstay of treatment to treat CRC includes different surgeries and chemotherapy. One such chemotherapy drug is Trifluridine-tipiracil (Lonsurf) an orally administered combination of the anticancer nucleoside analog trifluridine (FTD) and the thymidine phosphorylase inhibitor tipiracil.^[15] In this report, we described a patient who did not respond to the first two lines of major treatments. At first, the patient was given 6 cycles of Folfex + Avastin as First line palliative chemotherapy. He responded to this treatment plan initially but the tumor progressed and then he was switched to second-line therapy FOLFIRI + Ramucirumab. He also responded to this therapy initially and the tumor progressed. Then,

he received Lonsurf as third-line therapy. The failure of the first two lines of treatment has also been observed in previous studies. According to recent randomized clinical studies, the median progression-free survival for individuals treated with Ramucirumab -combined first-line chemotherapy was roughly 10 months.^[13] Even in the subgroup analysis, mCRC patients who received FOLFIRI with Ramucirumab as first-line therapy had progression-free survival of 8.9 months or longer (9.7 months; 95% CI 8.5–11.4).^[14] However, in our case, both treatment options failed as the patient developed hematemesis and severe gastric issues and there was no significant improvement in the patient's condition. Therefore, the failure of two first-line treatments within five months implies that the patient tumor might be rapidly advancing and has aggressive biology.^[15] It is also important to mention here, that the addition of an anti-epidermal growth factor receptor inhibitor (such as Ramucirumab) to one of the chemotherapy combinations is indicated to achieve the longest overall survival if the tumor does not possess a RAS mutation (OS).^[15] But our patient had RAS mutation, that could be why the first and second line of therapy was found to be ineffective in this case. However, the use of trifluoridine/tipiracil demonstrated promising therapeutic benefits. In addition, the study reported that trifluoridine/tipiracil was found to be very effective in the case of refractory metastatic CRC and patients were more likely to adhere to this treatment than those on Ramucirumab.^[16] Therefore, Lonsurf may be a reasonable therapeutic combination for patients who have progressed after two lines of major therapy, as suggested by this case report.

Lonsurf comprises two main drugs, namely Trifluridine and Tipiracil. Trifluridine is a thymidine-based nucleoside analog whereas Tipiracil works as an inhibitor of thymidine phosphorylase.^[17]

The recommended dosage for both these drugs is up to 35 mg/m², at least twice daily in a special protocol. Lonsurf is recommended to be taken at least an hour after the morning and evening meals. It is also important to get one's blood cell analysis done every two weeks.^[18]

Figure (A, B and C) Represents, the latest CT scan done in 2022.

Figure D and E: CEA response to Lonsurf.

CONCLUSION

Colorectal cancer (CRC) remains the third most prevalent cancer and the leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide. The prognosis is poor for people diagnosed with stage IV colon cancer along with peritoneal metastasis. Here we report a case of stage IV right-sided colon cancer complicated by ascites and peritoneal metastasis. The patient also had KRAS Mutant disease. This case was successfully treated with Lonsurf. This report suggests that Lonsurf may be a viable therapeutic combination for patients who have progressed following two major lines of treatment. However, future study is necessary to better understand its mechanism and develop biomarkers that more accurately predict its efficacy.

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